

Paper Archiving in the Zenodo Repository and in the UCT Prague Zenodo Community

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To publish a paper with an existing DOI on Zenodo under the UCT Prague Zenodo Community and include your ORCID, follow these step-by-step instructions:

Step 1: Create and/or Verify Your ORCID Profile

An ORCID iD is a unique identifier that distinguishes you from other researchers. Zenodo encourages adding your ORCID iD to your profile. If you don't have one, you can create it at <https://orcid.org/register>.

Step 2: Access the Zenodo Deposit Page

If you don't have a Zenodo account yet, you can create one using your ORCID or you can create a separate Zenodo account on the [Zenodo's homepage](https://zenodo.org).

Step 3: Create a New Deposit

With your account, to start creating a new deposit click on the "New upload" button or follow the link: <https://zenodo.org/uploads/new>. Using "Upload files" you can add the paper and supplementary information, if any.

Step 4: Fill in the Basic Information

- **Title:** Enter the title of your paper.
- **DOI:** **If the paper has a DOI, it must be copied and pasted into this repository.** Otherwise, the original journal article will not be linked to this repository, and if someone cites the new DOI, it will probably not be counted as a citation of the published paper. If you are sure that the paper does not have a DOI, you can reserve one.
- **Creators:** Include your ORCID by clicking on "Add Creator" and filling in your ORCID iD.
- **Publication Date:** Specify the publication date if it is different from the DOI creation date.
- **Related Works:** Enter the existing DOI for your paper.
- **License:** Choose the appropriate license for your work. **It must be the same license under which the paper is published,** often a [Creative Commons](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/) licence.
- **Description:** Describe your paper. Ideally, it should include an abstract.
- **Additional Description – Notes:** If you have any acknowledgement and/or want to specify funding (that cannot be included in the funding part), you can add it in an additional description.
- **Keywords:** Add relevant keywords to help other researchers find your work.
- **Related works:** Add any related works as published data, software, images, and so on.
- General recommendation: Data should be submitted to a repository prior to submission of a manuscript.

The screenshot displays the Zenodo upload interface. At the top, there is a search bar and navigation links for 'Communities' and 'My dashboard'. Below this, a yellow box highlights the 'Select the community where you want to submit your record.' prompt with a 'Select a community' button. The main content area is divided into 'Files' and 'Basic Information' sections. The 'Files' section shows storage availability (0 out of 100 files, 0 bytes out of 50.00 GB) and a 'Drag and drop files' area with an 'Upload files' button. The 'Basic Information' section is highlighted with a large yellow circle and contains the following fields:

- Digital Object Identifier:** A section asking 'Do you already have a DOI for this upload?' with 'Yes' and 'No' radio buttons. Below is a text input field for 'Copy/paste your existing DOI here...' and a note: 'A DOI allows your upload to be easily and unambiguously cited. Example: 10.1234/foa.bar'.
- Resource type:** A dropdown menu.
- Title:** A text input field with an 'Add titles' button below it.
- Publication date:** A date input field showing '2024-03-21' and a note: 'In case your upload was already published elsewhere, please use the date of the first publication. Format: YYYY-MM-DD, YYYYMM, or YYYY. For intervals use DATE/DATE, e.g. 1939/1945.'
- Creators:** A section with an 'Add creator' button.
- Description:** A rich text editor with a toolbar (Paragraph, Bold, Italic, Link, Unlink, Bulleted list, Numbered list, Indent, Outdent, Undo, Redo) and a text area. Below the editor is an 'Add description' button.
- Licenses:** A section showing 'Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International' with a 'Read more' link and 'Add standard' and 'Add custom' buttons.

On the right side of the interface, there is a 'Draft' section with 'Save draft', 'Preview', and 'Publish' buttons. Below that is a 'Visibility' section with 'Files only' and 'Public' (selected) options, and a note: 'The record and files are publicly accessible.' At the bottom right, there is an 'Options' section with an 'Apply an embargo' button and a note: 'Record or files protection must be restricted to apply an embargo.'

Step 7: Communities

Make sure you have selected the *UCT Prague Zenodo Community* (or any other relevant community) in the Communities section at the top of the page. This will ensure that your paper is associated with the UCT Prague Zenodo Community.

Note: Communities may also be added by the repository curator (creator of the deposit) after publishing. With the updates of Zenodo, all Communities must accept the content of your deposit before it is published! If you are in a hurry, consult your intent in advance to avoid delays.

Step 8: Versioning

If this is a new version of an existing publication, indicate the version number and provide a brief description of the changes.

Step 9: Save and Continue

Click the "Save" button to proceed.

Step 10: Review Your Information

Check all the information you have provided to ensure it is accurate. **After publishing on Zenodo, no changes to the files can be made.**

Step 11: Deposit Options

Choose the appropriate deposit options, including whether you want to publish the paper **immediately** or embargo it for a **certain amount of time**.

Step 12: Confirm and Deposit

Click the "Publish" button to confirm and deposit your paper in Zenodo. This will generate a new record with your existing DOI in the UCT Prague Zenodo Community.

Step 13: Confirmation

After your deposit is successfully published, Zenodo will provide you with a DOI for the new record. You can share this DOI with others to access your paper on Zenodo.